

Dyes Derived From 1:2:3-Quinolinetricarboxylic Acid.

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Acridic acid, which is 1:2-quinoline dicarboxylic acid, contains two carboxyl groups in *ortho* position to one another, and is therefore expected to yield dyestuffs on condensation with aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds just in the same way as phthalic acid or quinolinic acid (Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102).

Acridic acid differs from quinolinic acid in the same way as phthalic acid differs from naphthalic acid that is, by the presence in the latter of a fused benzene nucleus. From the point of view of the theory of colour that has been advanced by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171; also *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 99) it would be interesting to prepare pyronine dyestuffs from acridic acid and directly compare the intensity of their colour with the corresponding dyes derived from quinolinic acid, since by that means the effect of the fused benzene nucleus is easily ascertained. The effect of the nitrogen atom included in a ring system on colour, which is the main object of this series of papers, is also thereby seen by comparing colours of the dyes derived from acridic acid with the corresponding dyes derived from naphthalic acid. Hence it can be easily seen that from the theoretical point of view dyes derived from acridic acid, if they could be prepared, would be of considerable importance.

Unfortunately the only practicable method available for the preparation of acridic acid is by the oxidation of acridine by potassium permanganate. This method gives only about 10 per cent. yield of acridic acid, since in the oxidation reaction acridine is mainly transformed to pyridine tetracarboxylic acid, that is to say both the benzene nuclei in acridine are opened up by oxidation simultaneously, thereby considerably diminishing the yield of acridic acid. Besides this, the preparation of acridine itself in quantity is such a difficult affair, and the yield obtained is so bad, that for all intents and purposes acridic acid is practically an inaccessible material.

It was therefore thought that if some simple derivative of acridic acid could be fairly easily available, investigation could probably be

carried on with that substance instead of acridic acid itself. Amongst the higher homologues of acridine, 9-methyl-acridine can be prepared in good yield by the action of acetic acid and zinc chloride on diphenylamine at about 220° according to the method described by Fischer and Besthorn (*Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 74). This 9-methyl-acridine, on oxidation with potassium permanganate, gives an equally good yield of 1:2:3-quinoline-tricarboxylic acid, which is really 3-carboxy-acridic acid. The condensation of this acid with aromatic amino-, and hydroxy-compounds was therefore undertaken with the object of preparing dyestuffs which would be perfectly analogous in constitution to the corresponding dyes derived from acridic acid. Since a carboxyl in a dye molecule does not affect its colour to any appreciable extent as can be seen from the following table, it was therefore concluded that dyes derived from 3-carboxy-acridic acid would have practically the same colour as the corresponding dyes derived from acridic acid, and consequently would have the same theoretical importance.

<i>Dyestuffs.</i>	<i>Absorption maxima.</i>
Benzene-azo-phenol	4330
Benzene-azo-salicylic acid	4340
Benzene-azo- β -naphthol	4673
Benzene-azo- β -oxy-naphthoic acid	4680
Benzene-azo-pyrogallol	4430
Benzene-azo-gallic acid	4440
Benzene-azo-resorcinol	4470
Benzene-azo- β -resorcylic acid	4470

The only thing that remained to be settled was whether this 3-carboxyacridic acid would condense with aromatic amino-, and hydroxy-compounds in form I or II.

Form I was finally settled to be the form in which the condensations do actually occur by a study of the stability of the various pyridine carboxy-acids. Thus carbo-cinchomeric acid on careful heating can be made to decompose by successive losses of carboxyl into cinchomeric acid and finally into isonicotinic acid,

Similarly quinolinic acid on heating decomposes into nicotinic acid.

Thus it is evident that the further away the carboxyl group is from the heterocyclic nitrogen atom the less reactive and consequently the more stable it is. Hence, since in the condensation products of 3-carboxy-acridic acid with aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds one carboxyl is found to remain intact, it must be the 3-carboxyl group, since it is the least reactive of the three carboxyl groups present in the above acid. Therefore it follows that in all the condensation products of 3-carboxyacridic acid, it must have reacted in form I.

3-Carboxy-acridic acid condenses with aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds with remarkable ease, even without the use of any condensing agents, though of course the use of small quantities of strong sulphuric acid or tin tetrachloride is advisable in order to get increased yields of the resulting dyestuffs. The structure of the resorcinol compound is given below :—

The structures of other compounds described are quite analogous to this. The following aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds have been condensed with 3-carboxy-acridic acid and the resultant dyestuffs isolated :—phenol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, hydroxy-quinol, *m*-diethylamidophenol and *m*-phenylenediamine. The absorption spectra of these compounds will be given in a comparative tabular form along with the last paper of the series. Since

these dyestuffs contain a quinoline nucleus, it is expected that they might have photosensitising properties also. Further investigation in that direction is now in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensations of 3-carboxy-acridic acid with aromatic amino-, and hydroxy-compounds have been effected in the same manner as in the cases of β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid (Tewari and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 161) and imidazole dicarboxylic acid (Tewari and Dutt, *Ibid.*, 1927, 4, 201). The results are summarised in the following table:—

Dyes derived from 1:3:5-Quinoline-tricarboxylic acid.

Name.	Appearance.	M. p.	Colour in alkali.	Colour of fluorescence.	Analysis (calc. % in brackets).
Phenol-3-carboxy-acridin ...	Pale yellow needles.	Above 260°	Pink	C=69.3 (69.7); H=3.4 (3.04).
Resorcinol ..	Yellowish brown needles.	194°	Yellow	Yellow green	C=66.9 (67.4); H=3.2 (3.04).
Phloroglucinol ..	Orange needles	Above 260°	Orange red	C=63.02 (62.7); H=2.4 (2.8).
Hydroxyquinol ..	Brown needles	" "	Deep pink	C=68.1 (62.7); H=2.7 (2.8).
m-Diethylamidophenol ..	Pink needles	220°	Violet red (in acids).	Brown	N=7.4 (7.9).
m-Phenylethylenediamine ..	Dark brown	Above 260°	Yellow brown (in acids).	Green	N=13.9 (13.2).